

DIGITALISATION OF CULTURAL SPACE: PROBLEMS, ADVANTAGES, TRENDS

Kryvonos Ivan ¹, Kryvonos Iryna ² [0000-0001-7079-5150]

¹ student of the Faculty of Energy and Computer Technologies, Dmytro Motornyi Tavria State Agrotechnological University, Ukraine, ivan.a.krivonos@gmail.com

² senior Lecturer, Department of Foreign Languages, Dmytro Motornyi Tavria State Agrotechnological University, Ukraine, iryna.krivonos@tsatu.edu.ua

Abstract: The main trends in the culture of Ukraine today are highlighted in this paper and the main problems and advantages of the transition from the classical form of the authors' works to the digitalised one are justified. The use of artificial intelligence in design and relevant visual solutions that have been tested on their own experience are revealed.

Keywords: trends, culture, artificial intelligence, design, trends, digitalisation, globalisation, popularisation, recommendations.

Today, digitalisation is associated with the latest trend in information technologies, which, in fact, correlate with modern spheres of cultural life. The cultural component of our society is supplemented on a daily basis by the hostilities in Ukraine, which affect everyone, so we can see a certain tendency that almost any cultural manifestation is somehow connected to the war or its consequences and causes.

In the works of both domestic and foreign scholars the problems caused by digitalisation, are given special attention. A significant contribution to the study of this topic was made by researchers and scholars in various fields, including Andersson van der Heyden, A. Gurenko, Ya. Diakun, O. Zhehus, M. Ustenko and others.

Due to the fact that Ukrainian society is now scattered all over the country and in different parts of the world, it has become much more difficult than ever to communicate different types of culture and art, so more and more authors are getting involved in the process of digitalising their work.

It all starts with disclosing their activities online through advertising or full-fledged invitation videos and posters to a remote event, but sometimes it can be more global - part of exhibition or art projects, theatre as an audio tour, VR performances, cinema with 3D technologies, museums with holograms or 3D objects in the virtual reality dimension (Tregub, 2019).

In general, the idea of digitalisation has practical benefits: preserving artistic monuments and reaching a wider audience, engaging distant international organizations, etc. But it forces both artists and everyone involved to significantly modify their activities in order to be able to stay in the global network arena and not lose the quality of their product (Skakun, 2019).

It should be noted that nowadays the cultural space has also been greatly influenced by the sharp emergence of various types of artificial intelligence, some of which are capable of generating either in a certain area or completely from scratch any graphic solution prescribed by the user in a text field, which has several consequences of a different nature. At first sight, the work of artificial intelligence may seem amazing to an ordinary user, but for an experienced designer, the work of a computer is inaccurate, which will not allow it to completely replace a person. For example, artificial intelligence (A.I.) still cannot distinguish between objects sometimes, often does not take into account lighting and colour palette, generated objects and living creatures often have unnatural proportions and «blurred» features and details, and inaccuracies. However, many designers appreciate the fact that artificial intelligence can provide and visualize an idea, which saves time and the author's nervous system.

Therefore audiovisual content is a product that is currently in high demand. It should be noted that the transition from native to digital content is a personal matter for each author. However, we cannot ignore the global nature of this need in our country. Digitalisation would transform Ukraine, for example, at GOOGL&ART, from a white spot into a global cultural capital that can be visited online but is also worth visiting in person. Of course, a private initiative of cultural enthusiasts cannot become an internal «kitchen» for state museum institutions - this should be the responsibility of the relevant ministries, but such a platform will perfectly serve as an external relay of Ukrainian culture to the world.

Another point is the image and visibility of Ukraine in the international arena. We have a long history, a powerful creative class, and very educated people. But who knows about it? In addition to reputational needs, digitalisation also covers educational and scientific needs, because open access sources are a tasty morsel for researchers around the world. Now we don't have to fiercely prove how old Kyivan Rus is - digital facts and artefacts will speak for us (Skakun, 2019).

Due to the transition from native to digital display of their works, authors should understand that they will no longer be able to work for the target audience - the algorithms for displaying certain content differ on different resources, so you need to take into account the tastes of many people and expect even more criticism. Sometimes you even need to understand psychology to make the most accurate and timely decisions, because in the world of digitalisation and technology, anyone can give a critical comment on your work without any reason, and with some support from this person, the author can lose a large number of audience members.

Another component of successful digitalisation is being in line with trends. Artists and designers need to analyse the needs and preferences of the audience at the moment in order to attract even more online users to their works. It is important to understand that, along with the quality of the content and product itself, their presentation and design are also important. Here are some visual solutions offered by the Effect-M website (Morhun, 2021):

Motion animation - business tools should take into account design trends that consumers spend more time in the digital sphere, and you, as a brand or company, should make sure that their experience while performing these tasks is easy, pleasant and understandable. It is worth noting that motion design trends even affect packaging. Virtual reality is now very often used to read QR codes. This design is interesting, modern and interactive. Brand motion design is unique for each company and identifies the personal nature of communication with the consumer.

More aesthetics in design - this is how the «culture of fuss and material things» was abandoned and the focus shifted to self-care and determining one's own priorities in life. Trends in graphic design suggest using more aesthetics, updated minimalism, and cleanliness. There will be a growing number of brands whose visual message and messaging will have a cheerful meaning, reflecting warm, soft colour palettes and positive slogans.

Maximalism is going big - immersive visual experiences are replacing geometric, flat, austere brand systems. More and more companies are moving towards monochrome, bold palettes to create more expressive and user-friendly interfaces and exteriors.

Uncompromising realism and disruptive design - the so-called «disruptive» design requires action and participation. It will make the viewer question their own actions. Its distinctive features are a dark template and aggressive convictions that make you reject popular opinions and stereotypes.

Modern surrealism is a mixture of unverifiable surrealism and realism. Optical illusion styles create the impression of saturated colours and space. Another graphic trend that may emerge in the future is the combination of optical illusions with the parallax effect. At first glance, this may seem incomprehensible, even ridiculous, but it resonates with a large number of people (Morhun, 2021). We have implemented these trends in our work and our analytics have shown that these methods are really working now; we have noticed an increase in user reach, so we advise authors to try the above methods in their products and content. In conclusion, it should be noted that the process of digitising cultural works is not easy, and authors will need to acquire skills both in working in a computer environment and constantly monitor current trends and moods of a wide audience. However, it is important both personally for each designer and globally for Ukraine to expand the reach and interest of people not only locally but also abroad, with digitalisation being not only a means of distribution but also a means of preserving cultural landmarks of Ukrainian society.

References

1. Trehub, H. (2019). *Movoiu pikseliv ta baitiv*. Tyzhden. <https://tyzhden.ua/Culture/235178>
2. Skakun, I. (2019) «Kultura v smartfoni»: chomu potribna didzhytalizatsiia ukrainskoho natsionalnoho nadbannia Ukrainiska Pravda. <https://life.pravda.com.ua/columns/2019/11/6/238811>
3. Morhun, D. (2021). *Trendy hrafichnoho dyzainu 2022*. Effect M. <https://effect-m.com/uk/trendi-dizajnu-2022>